

Supplementary Figure S2. *Adar*^{5G1} neurodegeneration at 30 days.

Images of 6 micron thick haematoxylin and eosin stained sections through mushroom body calyces (left panels, (63X)) and retinas (right panels, 40X) of 30-day *Adar*^{5G1}.